

LocusZoom assessment for the regions where the top SNPs that had genome-wide significant associations ($P < 5 \times 10^{-8}$) were located within a ± 250 kb window using the imputed 1000 Genomes Project phase 3 reference panel data

Contents

1	Binary VBTs (The P/A or D/ND of bacterial taxa)	4
1.1	Phenotype 7. o_Bacteroidales (P/A)	4
2	Continuous VBTs (The extrapolated PICRUSt2 MetaCyc pathways)	7
2.1	Phenotype 2. ALL-CHORISMATE-PWY (superpathway of chorismate metabolism)	7
2.2	Phenotype 14. CATECHOL-ORTHO-CLEAVAGE-PWY (catechol degradation to β-keto adipate)	10
2.3	Phenotype 24. ENTBACSYN-PWY (enterobactin biosynthesis)	16
2.4	Phenotype 32. GALACT-GLUCUROCAT-PWY (superpathway of hexuronide and hexuronate degradation)	19
2.5	Phenotype P54. KDO-NAGLIPASYN-PWY (superpathway of (Kdo)2-lipid A biosynthesis)	22
2.6	Phenotype P56. LEU-DEG2-PWY (L-leucine degradation I)	25
2.7	Phenotype P64. P105-PWY (TCA cycle IV (2-oxoglutarate decarboxylase))	31
2.8	Phenotype P68. P125-PWY (superpathway of (R,R)-butanediol biosynthesis)	34
2.9	Phenotype P73. P221-PWY (octane oxidation)	37

2.10	Phenotype P90. PROTocatechuate-ortho-cleavage-PWY (protocatechuate degradation II (ortho-cleavage pathway))	43
2.11	Phenotype P93. PWY-1622 (formaldehyde assimilation I (serine pathway))	46
2.12	Phenotype P94. PWY-181 (photorespiration)	61
2.13	Phenotype P101. PWY-5005 (biotin biosynthesis II)	64
2.14	Phenotype P111. PWY-5180 (toluene degradation I (aerobic) (via o-cresol))	67
2.15	Phenotype P112. PWY-5182 (toluene degradation II (aerobic) (via 4-methylcatechol))	76
2.16	Phenotype P132. PWY-5741 (ethylmalonyl-CoA pathway)	82
2.17	Phenotype P133. PWY-5747 (2-methylcitrate cycle II)	100
2.18	Phenotype P177. PWY-6397 (mycolyl-arabinogalactan-peptidoglycan complex biosynthesis)	109
2.19	Phenotype P182. PWY-6507 (4-deoxy-L-threo-hex-4-enopyranuronate degradation)	112
2.20	Phenotype P185. PWY-6562 (norspermidine biosynthesis)	115
2.21	Phenotype P206. PWY-7007 (methyl ketone biosynthesis)	124
2.22	Phenotype P218. PWY-7211 (superpathway of pyrimidine deoxyribonucleotides de novo biosynthesis)	127
2.23	Phenotype P234. PWY-7373 (superpathway of demethylmenaquinol-6 biosynthesis II)	130
2.24	Phenotype P240. PWY-7456 (mannan degradation)	133
2.25	Phenotype P256. PWY0-1533 (methylphosphonate degradation I)	136
2.26	Phenotype P260. PWY0-321 (phenylacetate degradation I (aerobic))	139
2.27	Phenotype P288. TYRFUMCAT-PWY (L-tyrosine degradation I)	142
3	Continuous VBTs (The RAB of bacterial taxa)	145
3.1	Phenotype P4. c_Actinobacteria (RAB)	145
3.2	Phenotype P12. f_Bifidobacteriaceae (RAB)	148

3.3	Phenotype P24.	
	g_Streptococcus (RAB)	151
3.4	Phenotype P27.	
	s_Dialister microaerophilus (RAB)	154
3.5	Phenotype P28.	
	s_Dialister propionicifaciens (RAB)	157
3.6	Phenotype P33.	
	s_Lactobacillus jensenii (RAB)	160
3.7	Phenotype P34.	
	s_Lactobacillus mulieris (RAB)	169
4	Multivariate VBTs (Beta diversity)	172
4.1	Phenotype P2.	
	Unweighted Unifrac	172

1 Binary VBTs (The P/A or D/ND of bacterial taxa)

1.1 Phenotype 7.

o_Bacteroidales (P/A)

Chr10, rs7903692

date: Sun Apr 25 10:22:22 2021

build: hg19

display range: chr10:50338990–50838990 [50338990–50838990]

hilite range: 0 – 0 [0 – 0]

reference SNP: chr10:50588990

number of SNPs plotted: 1259

min P: 1.09E-7 [chr10:50591739]

max P: 10E-1 [chr10:50341918]

Make more plots at <http://csg.sph.umich.edu/locuszoom/>

2 Continuous VBTs (The extrapolated PICRUST2 MetaCyc pathways)

2.1 Phenotype 2.

ALL-CHORISMATE-PWY (superpathway of chorismate metabolism)

Chr14, rs146370889

date: Thu Apr 29 20:18:07 2021

build: hg19

display range: chr14:66194419-66694419 [66194419-66694419]

hilite range: 0 - 0 [0 - 0]

reference SNP: chr14:66444419

number of SNPs plotted: 1392

min P: 2.88E-8 [chr14:66444419]

max P: 9.99E-1 [chr14:66252937]

Make more plots at <http://csg.sph.umich.edu/locuszoom/>

2.2 Phenotype 14.

CATECHOL-ORTHO-CLEAVAGE-PWY (catechol degradation to β -ketoadipate)

Chr2, rs74685739

date: Thu Apr 29 18:11:07 2021

build: hg19

display range: chr2:142439916–142939916 [142439916–142939916]

hilite range: 0 – 0 [0 – 0]

reference SNP: chr2:142689916

number of SNPs plotted: 1390

min P: 1.42E-8 [chr2:142689916]

max P: 9.95E-1 [chr2:142837077]

Make more plots at <http://csg.sph.umich.edu/locuszoom/>

Chr10, rs150962471

date: Thu Apr 29 18:19:54 2021

build: hg19

display range: chr10:12775734–13275734 [12775734–13275734]

hilite range: 0 – 0 [0 – 0]

reference SNP: chr10:13025734

number of SNPs plotted: 2074

min P: 2.51E–10 [chr10:13022090]

max P: 10E–1 [chr10:13115604]

Make more plots at <http://csg.sph.umich.edu/locuszoom/>

2.3 Phenotype 24.
ENTBACSYN-PWY (enterobactin biosynthesis)

Chr14, rs146370889

date: Thu Apr 29 19:46:49 2021

build: hg19

display range: chr14:66194419-66694419 [66194419-66694419]

hilite range: 0 - 0 [0 - 0]

reference SNP: chr14:66444419

number of SNPs plotted: 1392

min P: 1.8E-8 [chr14:66444419]

max P: 10E-1 [chr14:66478364]

Make more plots at <http://csg.sph.umich.edu/locuszoom/>

2.4 Phenotype 32.
GALACT-GLUCUROCAT-PWY (superpathway of hexuronide and hexuronate degradation)

Chr8, rs117290187

date: Thu Apr 29 20:26:34 2021

build: hg19

display range: chr8:139624157-140124157 [139624157-140124157]

hilite range: 0 - 0 [0 - 0]

reference SNP: chr8:139874157

number of SNPs plotted: 1360

min P: 5E-8 [chr8:139874157]

max P: 9.97E-1 [chr8:139681587]

Make more plots at <http://csg.sph.umich.edu/locuszoom/>

2.5 Phenotype P54.

KDO-NAGLIPASYN-PWY (superpathway of (Kdo)2-lipid A biosynthesis)

Chr8, rs117290187

date: Thu Apr 29 20:35:02 2021

build: hg19

display range: chr8:139624157-140124157 [139624157-140124157]

hilite range: 0 - 0 [0 - 0]

reference SNP: chr8:139874157

number of SNPs plotted: 1360

min P: 1.4E-8 [chr8:139874157]

max P: 10E-1 [chr8:139993178]

Make more plots at <http://csg.sph.umich.edu/locuszoom/>

2.6 Phenotype P56.
LEU-DEG2-PWY (L-leucine degradation I)

Chr8, rs7842439

date: Thu Apr 29 20:46:39 2021

build: hg19

display range: chr8:13003898–13503898 [13003898–13503898]

hilite range: 0 – 0 [0 – 0]

reference SNP: chr8:13253898

number of SNPs plotted: 2595

min P: 4.11E–8 [chr8:13252863]

max P: 10E–1 [chr8:13044183]

Make more plots at <http://csg.sph.umich.edu/locuszoom/>

Chr11, rs1783557

date: Thu Apr 29 20:55:26 2021

build: hg19

display range: chr11:74969277-75469277 [74969277-75469277]

hilite range: 0 - 0 [0 - 0]

reference SNP: chr11:75219277

number of SNPs plotted: 1174

min P: 2.72E-5 [chr11:75219277]

max P: 9.99E-1 [chr11:75034238]

Make more plots at <http://csg.sph.umich.edu/locuszoom/>

2.7 Phenotype P64.

P105-PWY (TCA cycle IV (2-oxoglutarate decarboxylase))

Chr3, rs77485504

date: Thu Apr 29 21:02:49 2021

build: hg19

display range: chr3:194722515–195222515 [194722515–195222515]

hilite range: 0 – 0 [0 – 0]

reference SNP: chr3:194972515

number of SNPs plotted: 1896

min P: 4.79E–8 [chr3:194931080]

max P: 10E–1 [chr3:194822251]

Make more plots at <http://csg.sph.umich.edu/locuszoom/>

2.8 Phenotype P68.

P125-PWY (superpathway of (R,R)-butanediol biosynthesis)

Chr2, rs3796059

date: Thu Apr 29 21:12:03 2021

build: hg19

display range: chr2:10878962–11378962 [10878962–11378962]

hilite range: 0 – 0 [0 – 0]

reference SNP: chr2:11128962

number of SNPs plotted: 1653

min P: 1.37E–8 [chr2:11128962]

max P: 10E–1 [chr2:11131892]

Make more plots at <http://csg.sph.umich.edu/locuszoom/>

2.9 Phenotype P73.
P221-PWY (octane oxidation)

Chr6, rs12205331

date: Thu Apr 29 21:14:05 2021

build: hg19

display range: chr6:34648455–35148455 [34648455–35148455]

hilite range: 0 – 0 [0 – 0]

reference SNP: chr6:34898455

number of SNPs plotted: 1265

min P: 3.48E–11 [chr6:34898455]

max P: 9.99E–1 [chr6:34845648]

Make more plots at <http://csg.sph.umich.edu/locuszoom/>

Chr7, rs139478246

date: Thu Apr 29 21:21:18 2021

build: hg19

display range: chr7:49923835–50423835 [49923835–50423835]

hilite range: 0 – 0 [0 – 0]

reference SNP: chr7:50173835

number of SNPs plotted: 1147

min P: 4.57E-8 [chr7:50165778]

max P: 9.98E-1 [chr7:50143584]

Make more plots at <http://csg.sph.umich.edu/locuszoom/>

2.10 Phenotype P90.

PROTocatechuate-ortho-cleavage-PWY (protocatechuate degradation II (ortho-cleavage pathway))

Chr3, rs74529211

date: Thu Apr 29 21:31:07 2021

build: hg19

display range: chr3:25068339–25568339 [25068339–25568339]

hilite range: 0 – 0 [0 – 0]

reference SNP: chr3:25318339

number of SNPs plotted: 1822

min P: 3.24E–8 [chr3:25318339]

max P: 10E–1 [chr3:25177378]

Make more plots at <http://csg.sph.umich.edu/locuszoom/>

2.11 Phenotype P93.

PWY-1622 (formaldehyde assimilation I (serine pathway))

Chr1, rs75015030

date: Thu Apr 29 21:39:20 2021

build: hg19

display range: chr1:23336854–23836854 [23336854–23836854]

hilite range: 0 – 0 [0 – 0]

reference SNP: chr1:23586854

number of SNPs plotted: 832

min P: 4.64E–8 [chr1:23586854]

max P: 9.99E–1 [chr1:23679457]

Make more plots at <http://csg.sph.umich.edu/locuszoom/>

Chr1, rs144988916

date: Thu Apr 29 21:47:32 2021

build: hg19

display range: chr1:202384427-202884427 [202384427-202884427]

hilite range: 0 - 0 [0 - 0]

reference SNP: chr1:202634427

number of SNPs plotted: 1072

min P: 4.27E-9 [chr1:202634427]

max P: 9.98E-1 [chr1:202454053]

Make more plots at <http://csg.sph.umich.edu/locuszoom/>

Chr4, rs78166340

date: Thu Apr 29 21:56:39 2021

build: hg19

display range: chr4:70809109–71309109 [70809109–71309109]

hilite range: 0 – 0 [0 – 0]

reference SNP: chr4:71059109

number of SNPs plotted: 1642

min P: 2.66E-10 [chr4:71059109]

max P: 9.92E-1 [chr4:70827730]

Make more plots at <http://csg.sph.umich.edu/locuszoom/>

Chr6, rs141256380

date: Thu Apr 29 22:03:42 2021

build: hg19

display range: chr6:88294638–88794638 [88294638–88794638]

hilite range: 0 – 0 [0 – 0]

reference SNP: chr6:88544638

number of SNPs plotted: 1154

min P: 1.47E–9 [chr6:88634525]

max P: 1E0 [chr6:88690127]

Make more plots at <http://csg.sph.umich.edu/locuszoom/>

Chr7, rs61628535

date: Thu Apr 29 22:14:40 2021

build: hg19

display range: chr7:150623736–151123736 [150623736–151123736]

hilite range: 0 – 0 [0 – 0]

reference SNP: chr7:150873736

number of SNPs plotted: 1252

min P: 4.54E-11 [chr7:150873736]

max P: 9.99E-1 [chr7:151052147]

Make more plots at <http://csg.sph.umich.edu/locuszoom/>

2.12 Phenotype P94.
PWY-181 (photorespiration)

Chr7, rs61628535

date: Thu Apr 29 22:25:21 2021

build: hg19

display range: chr7:150623736–151123736 [150623736–151123736]

hilite range: 0 – 0 [0 – 0]

reference SNP: chr7:150873736

number of SNPs plotted: 1252

min P: 4.67E–8 [chr7:150873736]

max P: 10E–1 [chr7:150724324]

Make more plots at <http://csg.sph.umich.edu/locuszoom/>

2.13 Phenotype P101.
PWY-5005 (biotin biosynthesis II)

Chr10, rs10732902

date: Thu Apr 29 16:07:27 2021

build: hg19

display range: chr10:126447820-126947820 [126447820-126947820]

hilite range: 0 - 0 [0 - 0]

reference SNP: chr10:126697820

number of SNPs plotted: 1181

min P: 1.8E-9 [chr10:126709953]

max P: 10E-1 [chr10:126757924]

Make more plots at <http://csg.sph.umich.edu/locuszoom/>

2.14 Phenotype P111.

PWY-5180 (toluene degradation I (aerobic) (via o-cresol))

Chr6, rs12205331

date: Thu Apr 29 16:15:55 2021

build: hg19

display range: chr6:34648455–35148455 [34648455–35148455]

hilite range: 0 – 0 [0 – 0]

reference SNP: chr6:34898455

number of SNPs plotted: 1265

min P: 9.66E–11 [chr6:34898455]

max P: 9.98E–1 [chr6:34953738]

Make more plots at <http://csg.sph.umich.edu/locuszoom/>

Chr6, rs143842290

date: Thu Apr 29 16:25:47 2021

build: hg19

display range: chr6:169071987-169571987 [169071987-169571987]

hilite range: 0 - 0 [0 - 0]

reference SNP: chr6:169321987

number of SNPs plotted: 2426

min P: 2.11E-11 [chr6:169222366]

max P: 9.97E-1 [chr6:169463101]

Make more plots at <http://csg.sph.umich.edu/locuszoom/>

Chr17, rs58520434

date: Thu Apr 29 16:34:03 2021

build: hg19

display range: chr17:53396202–53896202 [53396202–53896202]

hilite range: 0 – 0 [0 – 0]

reference SNP: chr17:53646202

number of SNPs plotted: 1372

min P: 4.5E–10 [chr17:53646202]

max P: 10E–1 [chr17:53553655]

Make more plots at <http://csg.sph.umich.edu/locuszoom/>

2.15 Phenotype P112.

PWY-5182 (toluene degradation II (aerobic) (via 4-methylcatechol))

Chr6, rs17609940

date: Thu Apr 29 16:36:30 2021

build: hg19

display range: chr6:34784800–35284800 [34784800–35284800]

hilite range: 0 – 0 [0 – 0]

reference SNP: chr6:35034800

number of SNPs plotted: 1058

min P: 2.05E-8 [chr6:34898455]

max P: 9.96E-1 [chr6:35230077]

Make more plots at <http://csg.sph.umich.edu/locuszoom/>

Chr12, rs325099

date: Thu Apr 29 16:45:37 2021

build: hg19

display range: chr12:125598080-126098080 [125598080-126098080]

hilite range: 0 - 0 [0 - 0]

reference SNP: chr12:125848080

number of SNPs plotted: 1241

min P: 2.04E-8 [chr12:125848080]

max P: 10E-1 [chr12:126043123]

Make more plots at <http://csg.sph.umich.edu/locuszoom/>

2.16 Phenotype P132.
PWY-5741 (ethylmalonyl-CoA pathway)

Chr2, rs10170533

date: Thu Apr 29 16:55:23 2021

build: hg19

display range: chr2:170070151-170570151 [170070151-170570151]

hilite range: 0 - 0 [0 - 0]

reference SNP: chr2:170320151

number of SNPs plotted: 1473

min P: 2.48E-8 [chr2:170303817]

max P: 9.98E-1 [chr2:170473112]

Make more plots at <http://csg.sph.umich.edu/locuszoom/>

Chr6, rs151212088

date: Thu Apr 29 17:03:34 2021

build: hg19

display range: chr6:88338752-88838752 [88338752-88838752]

hilite range: 0 - 0 [0 - 0]

reference SNP: chr6:88588752

number of SNPs plotted: 1091

min P: 7.15E-12 [chr6:88634525]

max P: 9.99E-1 [chr6:88609666]

Make more plots at <http://csg.sph.umich.edu/locuszoom/>

Chr7, rs191956768

date: Thu Apr 29 17:12:20 2021

build: hg19

display range: chr7:23699362–24199362 [23699362–24199362]

hilite range: 0 – 0 [0 – 0]

reference SNP: chr7:23949362

number of SNPs plotted: 1695

min P: 3.66E–8 [chr7:23949362]

max P: 9.99E–1 [chr7:23838053]

Make more plots at <http://csg.sph.umich.edu/locuszoom/>

Chr8, rs147829035

date: Thu Apr 29 17:21:18 2021

build: hg19

display range: chr8:47610704–48110704 [47610704–48110704]

hilite range: 0 – 0 [0 – 0]

reference SNP: chr8:47860704

number of SNPs plotted: 864

min P: 2.18E–8 [chr8:47860704]

max P: 9.99E–1 [chr8:47761654]

Make more plots at <http://csg.sph.umich.edu/locuszoom/>

Chr10, rs186552055

date: Thu Apr 29 17:29:22 2021

build: hg19

display range: chr10:98480145-98980145 [98480145-98980145]

hilite range: 0 - 0 [0 - 0]

reference SNP: chr10:98730145

number of SNPs plotted: 919

min P: 1.72E-8 [chr10:98730145]

max P: 9.94E-1 [chr10:98915112]

Make more plots at <http://csg.sph.umich.edu/locuszoom/>

Chr19, rs190567288

date: Thu Apr 29 17:39:12 2021

build: hg19

display range: chr19:7962444-8462444 [7962444-8462444]

hilite range: 0 - 0 [0 - 0]

reference SNP: chr19:8212444

number of SNPs plotted: 1738

min P: 3.16E-8 [chr19:8212444]

max P: 10E-1 [chr19:8004990]

Make more plots at <http://csg.sph.umich.edu/locuszoom/>

2.17 Phenotype P133.
PWY-5747 (2-methylcitrate cycle II)

Chr1, rs1337195

date: Thu Apr 29 17:47:18 2021

build: hg19

display range: chr1:103304293–103804293 [103304293–103804293]

hilite range: 0 – 0 [0 – 0]

reference SNP: chr1:103554293

number of SNPs plotted: 1337

min P: 5.5E–9 [chr1:103554293]

max P: 9.92E–1 [chr1:103365785]

Make more plots at <http://csg.sph.umich.edu/locuszoom/>

Chr3, rs77485504

date: Thu Apr 29 17:56:11 2021

build: hg19

display range: chr3:194722515–195222515 [194722515–195222515]

hilite range: 0 – 0 [0 – 0]

reference SNP: chr3:194972515

number of SNPs plotted: 1896

min P: 1.69E–10 [chr3:194939542]

max P: 9.99E–1 [chr3:194930554]

Make more plots at <http://csg.sph.umich.edu/locuszoom/>

Chr6, rs10806401

date: Thu Apr 29 18:03:47 2021

build: hg19

display range: chr6:89665761-90165761 [89665761-90165761]

hilite range: 0 - 0 [0 - 0]

reference SNP: chr6:89915761

number of SNPs plotted: 1449

min P: 5.77E-9 [chr6:89878592]

max P: 9.98E-1 [chr6:89747291]

Make more plots at <http://csg.sph.umich.edu/locuszoom/>

2.18 Phenotype P177.

PWY-6397 (mycolyl-arabinogalactan-peptidoglycan complex biosynthesis)

Chr15, rs2622530

date: Thu Apr 29 18:30:14 2021

build: hg19

display range: chr15:100322954–100822954 [100322954–100822954]

hilite range: 0 – 0 [0 – 0]

reference SNP: chr15:100572954

number of SNPs plotted: 2598

min P: 1.81E–8 [chr15:100558556]

max P: 10E–1 [chr15:100668412]

Make more plots at <http://csg.sph.umich.edu/locuszoom/>

2.19 Phenotype P182.

PWY-6507 (4-deoxy-L-threo-hex-4-enopyranuronate degradation)

Chr8, rs117290187

date: Thu Apr 29 18:39:30 2021

build: hg19

display range: chr8:139624157-140124157 [139624157-140124157]

hilite range: 0 - 0 [0 - 0]

reference SNP: chr8:139874157

number of SNPs plotted: 1360

min P: 4.7E-8 [chr8:139874157]

max P: 9.98E-1 [chr8:140006609]

Make more plots at <http://csg.sph.umich.edu/locuszoom/>

2.20 Phenotype P185.
PWY-6562 (norspermidine biosynthesis)

Chr1, rs12401452

date: Thu Apr 29 18:48:04 2021

build: hg19

display range: chr1:203938459–204438459 [203938459–204438459]

hilite range: 0 – 0 [0 – 0]

reference SNP: chr1:204188459

number of SNPs plotted: 1178

min P: 3.7E–8 [chr1:204188459]

max P: 9.99E–1 [chr1:203966890]

Make more plots at <http://csg.sph.umich.edu/locuszoom/>

Chr2, rs117125246

date: Thu Apr 29 18:56:03 2021

build: hg19

display range: chr2:116200584–116700584 [116200584–116700584]

hilite range: 0 – 0 [0 – 0]

reference SNP: chr2:116450584

number of SNPs plotted: 1165

min P: 1.58E–8 [chr2:116450584]

max P: 9.98E–1 [chr2:116693608]

Make more plots at <http://csg.sph.umich.edu/locuszoom/>

Chr6, rs143842290

date: Thu Apr 29 19:04:18 2021

build: hg19

display range: chr6:169071987-169571987 [169071987-169571987]

hilite range: 0 - 0 [0 - 0]

reference SNP: chr6:169321987

number of SNPs plotted: 2426

min P: 2.05E-8 [chr6:169321987]

max P: 9.98E-1 [chr6:169163799]

Make more plots at <http://csg.sph.umich.edu/locuszoom/>

2.21 Phenotype P206.
PWY-7007 (methyl ketone biosynthesis)

Chr4, rs34676227

date: Thu Apr 29 19:12:37 2021

build: hg19

display range: chr4:24570114–25070114 [24570114–25070114]

hilite range: 0 – 0 [0 – 0]

reference SNP: chr4:24820114

number of SNPs plotted: 1546

min P: 2.87E–8 [chr4:24820114]

max P: 9.99E–1 [chr4:24901466]

Make more plots at <http://csg.sph.umich.edu/locuszoom/>

2.22 Phenotype P218.

PWY-7211 (superpathway of pyrimidine deoxyribonucleotides de novo biosynthesis)

Chr3, rs77485504

date: Thu Apr 29 19:20:08 2021

build: hg19

display range: chr3:194722515–195222515 [194722515–195222515]

hilite range: 0 – 0 [0 – 0]

reference SNP: chr3:194972515

number of SNPs plotted: 1896

min P: 2.56E–8 [chr3:194973448]

max P: 10E–1 [chr3:194839132]

Make more plots at <http://csg.sph.umich.edu/locuszoom/>

2.23 Phenotype P234.

PWY-7373 (superpathway of demethylmenaquinol-6 biosynthesis II)

Chr10, rs12766353

date: Thu Apr 29 19:30:13 2021

build: hg19

display range: chr10:134052618-134552618 [134052618-134552618]

hilite range: 0 - 0 [0 - 0]

reference SNP: chr10:134302618

number of SNPs plotted: 1235

min P: 3.86E-9 [chr10:134295039]

max P: 9.98E-1 [chr10:134242197]

Make more plots at <http://csg.sph.umich.edu/locuszoom/>

2.24 Phenotype P240.
PWY-7456 (mannan degradation)

Chr8, rs117290187

date: Thu Apr 29 19:38:46 2021

build: hg19

display range: chr8:139624157-140124157 [139624157-140124157]

hilite range: 0 - 0 [0 - 0]

reference SNP: chr8:139874157

number of SNPs plotted: 1360

min P: 2.99E-9 [chr8:139874157]

max P: 9.97E-1 [chr8:139920951]

Make more plots at <http://csg.sph.umich.edu/locuszoom/>

2.25 Phenotype P256.
PWY0-1533 (methylphosphonate degradation I)

Chr14, rs146370889

date: Thu Apr 29 19:54:52 2021

build: hg19

display range: chr14:66194419-66694419 [66194419-66694419]

hilite range: 0 - 0 [0 - 0]

reference SNP: chr14:66444419

number of SNPs plotted: 1392

min P: 3.4E-8 [chr14:66444419]

max P: 9.98E-1 [chr14:66289350]

Make more plots at <http://csg.sph.umich.edu/locuszoom/>

2.26 Phenotype P260.
PWY0-321 (phenylacetate degradation I (aerobic))

Chr2, rs13004173

date: Thu Apr 29 20:03:25 2021

build: hg19

display range: chr2:30331537-30831537 [30331537-30831537]

hilite range: 0 - 0 [0 - 0]

reference SNP: chr2:30581537

number of SNPs plotted: 1277

min P: 1.73E-8 [chr2:30578049]

max P: 9.98E-1 [chr2:30732948]

Make more plots at <http://csg.sph.umich.edu/locuszoom/>

2.27 Phenotype P288.
TYRFUMCAT-PWY (L-tyrosine degradation I)

Chr12, rs11831423

date: Thu Apr 29 20:10:38 2021

build: hg19

display range: chr12:91800203–92300203 [91800203–92300203]

hilite range: 0 – 0 [0 – 0]

reference SNP: chr12:92050203

number of SNPs plotted: 929

min P: 1.2E-8 [chr12:92050203]

max P: 9.99E-1 [chr12:92014180]

Make more plots at <http://csg.sph.umich.edu/locuszoom/>

3 Continuous VBTs (The RAB of bacterial taxa)

3.1 Phenotype P4. c_Actinobacteria (RAB)

Chr10, rs303212

date: Sun Apr 25 19:43:14 2021

build: hg19

display range: chr10:90911355-91411355 [90911355-91411355]

hilite range: 0 - 0 [0 - 0]

reference SNP: chr10:91161355

number of SNPs plotted: 1278

min P: 2.34E-8 [chr10:91161355]

max P: 9.98E-1 [chr10:91244637]

Make more plots at <http://csg.sph.umich.edu/locuszoom/>

3.2 Phenotype P12.

f_Bifidobacteriaceae (RAB)

Chr10, rs303212

date: Sun Apr 25 18:22:07 2021

build: hg19

display range: chr10:90911355-91411355 [90911355-91411355]

hilite range: 0 - 0 [0 - 0]

reference SNP: chr10:91161355

number of SNPs plotted: 1278

min P: 3.12E-8 [chr10:91161355]

max P: 9.99E-1 [chr10:91330137]

Make more plots at <http://csg.sph.umich.edu/locuszoom/>

3.3 Phenotype P24. g_Streptococcus (RAB)

Chr19, rs272406

date: Sun Apr 25 18:35:44 2021

build: hg19

display range: chr19:54850503–55350503 [54850503–55350503]

hilite range: 0 – 0 [0 – 0]

reference SNP: chr19:55100503

number of SNPs plotted: 1936

min P: 7.43E-4 [chr19:55086775]

max P: 9.97E-1 [chr19:54987609]

Make more plots at <http://csg.sph.umich.edu/locuszoom/>

3.4 Phenotype P27.

s_Dialister micraerophilus (RAB)

Chr3, rs368422065

date: Sun Apr 25 18:45:01 2021

build: hg19

display range: chr3:88247234-88747234 [88247234-88747234]

hilite range: 0 - 0 [0 - 0]

reference SNP: chr3:88497234

number of SNPs plotted: 1827

min P: 1.19E-8 [chr3:88497234]

max P: 9.98E-1 [chr3:88733658]

Make more plots at <http://csg.sph.umich.edu/locuszoom/>

3.5 Phenotype P28.

s_*Dialister propionificiens* (RAB)

Chr4, rs117189532

date: Sun Apr 25 18:53:21 2021

build: hg19

display range: chr4:109896332-110396332 [109896332-110396332]

hilite range: 0 - 0 [0 - 0]

reference SNP: chr4:110146332

number of SNPs plotted: 1389

min P: 5.16E-9 [chr4:110146332]

max P: 9.98E-1 [chr4:110022474]

Make more plots at <http://csg.sph.umich.edu/locuszoom/>

3.6 Phenotype P33. s_Lactobacillus jensenii (RAB)

Chr2, rs7599669

date: Sun Apr 25 19:04:31 2021

build: hg19

display range: chr2:5275802-5775802 [5275802-5775802]

hilite range: 0 - 0 [0 - 0]

reference SNP: chr2:5525802

number of SNPs plotted: 1022

min P: 7.4E-9 [chr2:5521574]

max P: 9.97E-1 [chr2:5625445]

Make more plots at <http://csg.sph.umich.edu/locuszoom/>

Chr4, rs76261874

date: Sun Apr 25 19:14:34 2021

build: hg19

display range: chr4:39430065–39930065 [39430065–39930065]

hilite range: 0 – 0 [0 – 0]

reference SNP: chr4:39680065

number of SNPs plotted: 1392

min P: 3.86E–8 [chr4:39680065]

max P: 9.99E–1 [chr4:39713743]

Make more plots at <http://csg.sph.umich.edu/locuszoom/>

Chr4, rs74667312

date: Sun Apr 25 19:24:26 2021

build: hg19

display range: chr4:66573772-67073772 [66573772-67073772]

hilite range: 0 - 0 [0 - 0]

reference SNP: chr4:66823772

number of SNPs plotted: 1670

min P: 1.93E-8 [chr4:66823772]

max P: 10E-1 [chr4:66625896]

Make more plots at <http://csg.sph.umich.edu/locuszoom/>

3.7 Phenotype P34.

s_Lactobacillus mulieris (RAB)

Chr4, rs75042393

date: Sun Apr 25 19:32:48 2021

build: hg19

display range: chr4:107932727-108432727 [107932727-108432727]

hilite range: 0 - 0 [0 - 0]

reference SNP: chr4:108182727

number of SNPs plotted: 1403

min P: 2.48E-10 [chr4:108184444]

max P: 9.98E-1 [chr4:107958420]

Make more plots at <http://csg.sph.umich.edu/locuszoom/>

4 Multivariate VBTs (Beta diversity)

4.1 Phenotype P2. Unweighted Unifrac

Chr8, rs117290187

date: Wed May 5 09:14:33 2021

build: hg19

display range: chr8:139624157-140124157 [139624157-140124157]

hilite range: 0 - 0 [0 - 0]

reference SNP: chr8:139874157

number of SNPs plotted: 1360

min P: 9.38E-9 [chr8:139874157]

max P: 9.97E-1 [chr8:139759604]

Make more plots at <http://csg.sph.umich.edu/locuszoom/>